

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report summarizes the ability of the high-resolution models in representing a realistic near-surface meteorology. It presents a comparison of storm-resolving model runs against data from coarse resolution simulations and from observational sites.

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WP8

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1 Executive summary

In this study, we present a first evaluation of global storm resolving models and their ability to capture diurnal variability over land. We particularly focus on how the combination of resolving storms and resolving landscapes (detailed land-use and orography) at kilometer-scale resolutions impacts the energy and water balance. Two prototypes storm-resolving models (ICON and IFS) are compared with each other and observations, to validate if there is an agreement in signal when moving to storm-resolving resolutions. We both show global maps of diurnal variability and local analysis at various locations with the aim to assess when and where results are sensitive to spatial resolution. We highlight new insights, but also model shortcomings that this study has revealed that need attention.

2 Conclusion & Results

The most important results and conclusions drawn from this report are:

- Storm-resolving models are the best generation of models to date in their ability to reproduce 2-m surface air temperature, but there is a large spread in quality among the simulations.
- Both ICON and IFS reproduce patterns in the energy, water, and momentum balance that resemble reality, but at the same time large discrepancies exist between the models.
- ICON has considerably more net radiation at the surface than IFS, mainly driven by higher surface solar irradiance fluxes.
- ICON uses more of the available energy at the surface for sensible heating and less for latent heating compared to IFS.
- Both ICON, IFS and ERA5 show summer afternoon precipitation peak over the Alps earlier during the day than observed
- ICON shows larger diurnal temperature ranges compared to IFS over the Alps, and IFS is in better correspondence with observations

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	yes
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	yes

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Evaluate surface energy, water and momentum balance components as well as near-surface meteorology over land at storm-resolving resolution against observations and coarser resolution simulations (O1)	yes
Represent land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolution by making use of the latest generation remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation (O1)	yes
Prepare the NextGEMS models to best serve the science and applications, by implementing online output statistics co-developed with stakeholders, with a pilot project focusing on solar energy (O1 and O3)	yes

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Expand scope of the SR-ESM by coupling it offline to a terrestrial biosphere model (O1)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Introduction

We expect that storm resolving models can produce a more realistic climate over land by removing long-standing biases related to the parameterization of convection and the limited detail at which the landscape is resolved in the current generation of models.

In short, global storm resolving models are able to resolve local weather phenomena such as mountain winds or deep convective systems, which traditionally required the use of regional climate models. Consequently, unlike regional models, storm-resolving models can also benefit from the upscale effects of well-resolved storms and landscapes to the global circulation. Also from a practical perspective the benefits are large, as many regional climate studies simplify to a data analysis exercise as data from storm resolving models is available for any location of the globe.

With the global storm-resolving models still in their infancy, careful analysis is needed to study to which extent the models live up to their promise. In nextGEMS, it has been demonstrated that the endeavor is technically feasible, and many scientific studies are emerging that study and compare the two storm-resolving models.

In this document, we present the results of deliverable 8.1 that should provide a first insight in how well the ICON and IFS model are representing the climate over land. In this deliverable we compare the components of the surface energy budget, water cycle, and momentum balance for the two storm-resolving models and compare against coarse resolution simulations and observations.

Before outlining the plan for analysis, we would like emphasize that the storm-resolving models used in nextGEMS are under continuous and fast development, and that the results presented here are produced with models that have already been improved in their representation of the land surface. Also, at the moment of writing, the available simulation length was 5 years, hence the seasonal statistics have not yet converged.

The strategy of this report will be the following. We will first present the overall ability of nextGEMS simulations to represent the global 2 m surface air temperature in comparison to earlier model intercomparison projects.

Subsequently, we will show a selection of variables that present a comprehensive overview of the performance of storm-resolving models on the global scale. We will compare the models against each other, against ERA5 Hersbach et al., 2020 reanalys data, which represents observations, and to coarse resolution simulations.

To validate the surface energy balance, we decided to first focus on the net radiation as it carries information from both resolved storms, as well as the details of the landscape. We make use of its independent shortwave and longwave components and cloud information to interpret the energy balance. Second, we will analyse the partitioning of the surface fluxes into sensible and latent heat to see how available energy reenters the atmosphere and drives the water cycle.

Third, we will analyse the diurnal cycle of wind, to study whether resolving the landscape and the largest modes of convection improves the diurnal cycle with respect to coarse resolution models. Fourth, we analyse soil-moisture precipitation coupling as this is where storm-resolving models are expected to outperform coarse resolution models, due to better spatial patterns of soil moisture and resolving the larger modes of convection.

We will end our analyses by presenting a number of case studies for which we expect that resolving storms and landscapes will increase the quality of the simulations. We are aware that there is a certain level of arbitrariness to this selection, but at the same time, we expect to be able to draw some preliminary conclusions on the (existence of) benefits of storm-resolving model resolution.

4.2 Model configurations used in this deliverable

4.2.1 IFS

The simulations used here are coupled simulations of the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS 48r1) and the Finite Volume Sea ice-Ocean Model (FESOM2.5) produced as Cycle 3 of the nextGEMS simulations (i.e. third phase of this development cycle). IFS is run with a spectral resolution of TCo2559, corresponding to a horizontal grid of 4.4 km. The ocean has a variable grid resolution NG5 that reaches locally 5 km. In the simulations at 4.4km, instead of switching the deep convection scheme off completely, its activity is strongly reduced (the cloud base mass flux is reduced by a factor of 5 compared to the default value). The land model of IFS is called ECLand Boussetta et al. (2021) and contains a 4-layer soil scheme, a lake model, an urban model, a vegetation model, and a multi-layer snow scheme. The urban scheme was activated for the first time in the Cycle 3 simulations (see McNorton et al. (2023)). A new set of surface fields was implemented, including new land cover/land use maps from ESA-CCI, a monthly climatology of leaf area index, and a new ocean bathymetry based on GEBCO2021. More details on the simulation and model set-up can be found in an upcoming paper by Rackow et al.

Simulations are performed from 20 January 2020 onwards for five years. The simulations were performed with constant greenhouse gas forcing from the year 2020 (CO₂ = 413.72 ppmv, 267 CH₄ = 1914.28 ppbv, N₂O = 331.80 ppbv, CFC11 = 857.38 pptv, CFC12 = 497.10 pptv), prognostic ozone, no volcanic 268 aerosols, and the CAMS aerosol climatology (Bozzo et al. 2020).

4.2.2 ICON

For the simulation using the ICON storm-resolving model, the ICON-Sapphire configuration is used, which is designed for kilometer scale simulation. A detailed description of the ICON-Sapphire configuration is provided by Hohenegger et al. (2023), but the Cycle 3 ICON 5 km simulation contains some updates. The radiation is parameterized by the Radiative Transfer for Energetics RRTM for General circulation model applications-Parallel (RTE-RRTMGP) scheme, instead of the Psrad scheme. Modifications to fix bugs found in the ICON Cycle 3 include ocean

surface coupling in the turbulence scheme, energy changes in the microphysics scheme, and river discharge coupling with the ocean in the land surface model. Additionally, land input data is updated with high-resolution fraction of the land, lake, and glacier, and soil texture parameter.

The Cycle 3 ICON 5 km simulation is integrated at a grid spacing of 5 km, for 5 years starting from 20 January 2020. The atmosphere has 90 vertical layers and the land consists of five soil layers. In order to have the energy balance and a reasonable amount of cloud over the ocean, the cloud inhomogeneity factor is set to 0.6, reducing reflected shortwave radiation. The simulation output is written in multiple zoom levels on the Hierarchical Equal Area isoLatitude Pixelization (HEALPix) grid. Reading and analyzing the data on the HEALPix grid speeds up and minimizes data loading.

4.3 Comparison of model runs

The simulations presented in section 4.4.2 and beyond are part of the Cycle 3 stage. IFS-28km is a IFS run with 28 by 28 km horizontal resolution, IFS-4.4 is the IFS run with 4.4 by 4.4 km² resolution, and ICON-5km is the ICON run with 5 by 5 km² horizontal resolution.

With these simulations, we define the following differences that can be computed for any variable:

- IFS-4.4 - IFS-28 is the *resolution difference*
- IFS-4.4 - ICON-5 is the *model difference*
- IFS-4.4 - OBS is the *IFS difference to observations*
- ICON-5 - OBS is the *ICON difference to observations*

In this report, we would like to assess what we "get for free" by running global simulations at high spatial resolution. Answering this question for a specific variable would require the resolution difference to be larger than the model difference, this showing that increase in resolution has a stronger impact than switching between models at the same resolution. Ideally, one would compute the resolution difference both with ICON and IFS, but this data is currently unavailable to the nextGEMS community.

4.4 Results

4.4.1 The 2-m surface air temperature

The 2-m surface air temperature is the most widely studied variable in the broad theme of climate change and the variable in which global warming in models is typically expressed. Figure 1 compares to which extent the produced 20-year mean near-surface temperature climate in nextGEMS runs resemble observation-based datasets and how they compare to earlier model intercomparison projects. This particular analysis takes advantage of the most recent nextGEMS simulations (ICON-ngc4008, IFS9-prod), which represent the early stages of the

Figure 1: Boxplots representing the fraction of the total global area for which each model falls within the distribution of the eight observation-based datasets (black markers) in different model intercomparison projects. The closer the models are to the vertically oriented dashed line, the more frequently they are indistinguishable from observations. The different nextGEMS-related runs are indicated with pink markers and specified here: ICON-ngc2013: Cycle 2; 10km atmosphere, IFS4.4: cycle 3; 4.4km; IFS4.4-FESOM5-cycle3, IFS28: Cycle 3; 28km; IFS28-FESOM25-cycle3, ICON-ngc4008: Cycle 4, IFS9prod: cycle 4; 9km, ICON-ESM: EERIE Cycle 1; 10km, IFS-FESOM; EERIE/FESOM; production; 9km. Unfiled markers indicate models with less than 20 years available. **This figure is courtesy of Lukas Brunner (University of Vienna), this report will be under embargo until a scientific publication with this figure has been released.**

production runs with longer data records. Each model is evaluated against eight observation-based references on a grid cell basis. The area-weighted fraction of grid cells where the models fall within the full range of the observations is calculated. An indication of the magnitude of internal variability in this comparison is given by the inclusion of a 44-member single model initial condition large ensemble (SMILE). In the bottommost boxplot, the reference datasets are evaluated against each other in a leave-one-out cross-validation setting.

The figure, in which the intercomparison projects are sorted chronologically by generation (and implicitly also by resolution, given the increase in computing power), shows that the quality of the models is increasing with model resolution and that the best nextGEMS runs (IFS28 and IFS-FESOM) are the simulation with the best match with observations from the entire set, with IFS-FESOM getting close to the performance of some of the reference datasets (black symbols). However, it also shows that recent ICON runs (ICON-ngc4008, ICON-ESM) compare to the CMIP6 runs near the lower quartile in their representation of 2 m temperature, and that the match with observations for the ICON runs had reduced from Cycle 2 onwards. Nonetheless, given the infancy of the storm-resolving models, and the already good match with observations compared to earlier intercomparison projects, we could argue that there is perspective for the storm-resolving models for becoming the best models to date.

Figure 2: Global net radiation in the months June-July-August averaged over the entire 5Y dataset for both models. Panels a and b show the net radiation, c and d the model quality for both models, e) the model difference and f) the resolution difference. The ERA5 reference is based on 33 years of data (1990-2022).

4.4.2 The surface radiation balance

The next variable we analyse is net radiation, the net balance of incoming and outgoing solar and thermal radiation fluxes as it provides a comprehensive insight in the near-surface climate. This variable is strongly influenced by clouds, and in turn feeds back to cloudiness by regulating the surface heat fluxes. Also, the net radiation closely couples to land surface properties, in particular via albedo, hence the more detailed land-use maps that are used in the storm-resolving models could have a strong impact on the net radiation. With our focus on the land surface, we have chosen for a seasonal average over the months June, July, and August as this contains the strongest signal of convective clouds and land surface processes.

Figure 2 shows the net radiation as produced by IFS and ICON, and the model quality, model difference, and resolution sensitivity. This figure shows that both models produce comparable global patterns of net radiation over land, with the highest values in vegetated regions in the northern subtropics, and lower values in deserts in northern Africa and Arabia. These lower values are likely explained by greater energy loss from outgoing shortwave due to a higher albedo and from outgoing longwave radiation due to high surface temperatures, compared to

vegetated surfaces at similar latitudes.

Compared to ERA5, ICON has considerably more net radiation, with values in the range of 25 to 50 W m^{-2} more, whereas IFS is comparable. Consequently, the difference between ICON and IFS is very comparable to the model error of ICON. The net radiation biases are present on the entire continental Northern Hemisphere, with little spatial variation, showing that net radiation biases do not strongly relate to regional climate or land use type. The strongest differences are found near the eastern and western shores of the Red Sea, as well as on the slopes of the Greenlandic coast. We will interpret the differences with the help of the figure below.

Figure 3: Further interpretation of the radiation balance. The ERA5 reference is based on 33 years of data (1990-2022)

Figure 3 sheds further light on the observed differences in net radiation. The most striking difference between ICON and IFS is the incoming shortwave radiation, that is in nearly all locations up to 100 W m^{-2} higher. Differences are high independent of the presence of liquid water and ice, indicating that the atmosphere is more transparent for clear-sky radiation in ICON, most logically due to a lower aerosol optical depth. Differences reduce in (sub-)tropical West Africa, where both models produce a high cloud cover.

Part of the difference in shortwave radiation is compensated by downwelling longwave. In particular at low latitudes less radiation is received at the surface in the ICON simulations, also hinting at an overall lower emissivity. Unlike the net radiation plot (Fig. 2), the total downwelling radiation has regions where ICON exceeds IFS, but this is compensated by a reduction in upwelling longwave radiation, due to lower temperatures in ICON in low latitudes. The lower upwelling longwave radiation is mainly the effect of the absence of a skin layer in ICON, resulting in weaker response of surface temperature to radiation.

In the end, the excess energy of ICON is mainly converted into sensible heating as its evaporative fraction $EF = LE / (H + LE)$ (fraction of the available energy $H + LE$ used for evapotranspiration) is less than that of IFS. In the next subsection we look deeper into this variable.

4.4.3 Evaporative fraction as a measure to study sensible and latent heat fluxes

The variations in net surface radiation that we analyzed in the previous section enter the earth system via the surface sensible and latent heat fluxes. We have chosen to condense the two into the evaporative fraction to enable comparison with Figure 2 from the previous section, and because EF connects strongly with land surface properties such as vegetation, soil moisture. Figure 4 shows the evaporative fraction, model quality, and the impact of resolution.

In this figure, we see that IFS and ICON have similar global patterns, but also show large regions with large differences in surface flux regimes among the models. For instance, this is prominent in central US and Canada, large parts of the Eurasia, which all have a lower EF in ICON, whereas Australia, India, and (the sahel region in) Africa show a larger EF in ICON. These results show that in the midlatitudes the fraction of the available energy spent on evapotranspiration is considerably larger in IFS than in ICON, likely due to more available soil moisture caused by more precipitation (not shown). In the subtropics (~ 30 degrees N and S) on both hemispheres, ICON produces more evapotranspiration than IFS, which is driven by the presence of clouds with a higher water and ice content (see Fig. 3g) leading to more precipitation.

Compared to ERA5, both models are drier over a large part of Asia (mainly in the range between 30 and 50 degrees N), Africa between 20 and 30 degrees south, and the tip of South America (see Fig. 3c, d). Given the consistency between the two models over such a large area and the short duration of the runs, the average states of the oceans in the two models, which strongly influence the precipitation and hence the soil moisture, are probably driving these biases. The shorter time averages in ICON and IFS compared to the 30-year average taken from the ERA5 data is a major contributor. We leave Greenland out of the discussion due to the omnipresence of ice and $H + LE$ changing sign there, making the evaporative fraction hard to interpret.

4.4.4 Wind

Near-surface winds are driven both by large-scale synoptic systems and local surface characteristics such as land use type (e.g. roughness, heat capacity) and orography. As storm-resolving models use more detailed land-use maps than their coarser resolution counterparts, we would expect a strong impact of horizontal resolution on the representation of local wind phenomena

Figure 4: Evaporative fraction calculated from the June-July-August means of sensible and latent heat flux. Panels a and b show the evaporative fraction for the models, c and d the model quality for both models, e) the model difference and f) the resolution difference. The ERA5 reference is based on 33 years of data (1990-2022)

such as land-sea breezes or mountain winds. Since near-surface wind speeds may have clear diurnal variability, driven by the heating and cooling of the land surface, we now focus on the diurnal cycle of the 10-meter wind speed.

Figure 5 shows the range in the mean diurnal cycle of the 10-meter wind speed in boreal summer (June, July, August, 2020 – 2024) as produced by the IFS and ICON simulations, as well as the quality of the models with respect to ERA5, the difference between the models, and the sensitivity to horizontal resolution. Both models show similar global patterns and large diurnal variations in wind speed over most regions with relatively large orographic variability (a noticeable exception is Antarctica, where katabatic winds remain strong throughout the day). Both models also produce stronger diurnal cycles in those mountainous areas than ERA5, with ICON showing larger differences than IFS.

The larger diurnal cycles are likely the result of the better-resolved gradients in surface elevation at higher horizontal resolution, which may suggest the storm-resolving models are more realistic than ERA5. However, differences between the 4.4 km and 28 km IFS runs are generally smaller than the difference between IFS and ERA5, indicating that the impact of horizontal

resolution is relatively small. Nonetheless, the resolution difference is most prominent in areas in complex terrain and near coastlines, which confirms our hypothesis that resolution is most important in these areas. Furthermore, we find that the impact of horizontal resolution is small compared to the difference between the storm-resolving ICON and IFS simulations, showing that the representation of surface wind speed variability is affected more by model design than by resolution.

Figure 5: Range in the mean diurnal cycle of the 10-meter wind speeds, averaged over June, July and August, 2020 – 2024. First the mean diurnal cycle of wind speed U is computed from the half hourly (ICON) and hourly (IFS, ERA5) values of the zonal v and meridional u winds ($U = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}$). The range is then the difference between the highest and lowest value of the mean diurnal cycle. Panels a and b show the mean diurnal cycle of both models, c and d the model quality for both models, e) the model difference and f) the resolution difference. The ERA5 reference is based on 33 years of data (1990-2022)

4.4.5 Soil moisture-precipitation coupling

The last part of the global analysis involves the soil moisture-precipitation coupling. One of the hopes of storm-resolving models is that by resolving larger deep convective systems, they provide a more realistic link between soil moisture anomalies and precipitation formation over

land.

Taylor et al. (2012) found that the spatial relationship between soil-moisture anomalies and afternoon precipitation is mostly positive in global circulation models and ERA-interim, whereas they found it to be mostly negative in data derived from satellite observations. Guillod et al. (2015) continued this work by investigating temporal and heterogeneity preferences of rainfall. They found that it rains more in relatively dry conditions (spatially) when the general conditions are wetter (temporally) and heterogeneous. Moon et al. (2019) compared the three preferences - spatial, temporal, and heterogeneity - in observations and in nine CMIP5 models. Similarly to Taylor et al. (2012), they found a dominantly negative spatial feedback in observations and a dominantly positive spatial feedback in the models. The temporal feedback shows more agreement between models and observations, but there are still several regions with high intermodel variability and disagreement with observations. The heterogeneity preference in the models shows a similar pattern to the temporal preference, whereas this is not the case in the observations where it is dominantly positive or nonsignificant. Here, we explore if resolved deep convection in the ICON model and mostly resolved deep convection in the IFS model will bring the signs and global patterns of the soil moisture-precipitation feedbacks closer to observations.

We follow the methods by Taylor et al. (2012), Guillod et al. (2015), and Moon et al. (2019) which comprise of the following steps: Precipitation and rootzone soil moisture index (SMI) data are regridded from the native grid to a latitude and longitude grid of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$. Daily accumulated morning (6-12 LST) precipitation (P_m) and afternoon (12-24 LST) precipitation (P_a) are calculated. The seasonal (31-day) mean SMI is subtracted from the SMI to get the SMI-anomaly (S'). Event samples (Y_e) are defined as the locations of P_a maxima (L_{max}) within an event domain of $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ grid cells centered at the P_a maximum. Event samples are valid when $P_a > 4$ mm, there is no water body in the event domain, and $P_m < 1$ mm. The locations of the P_a minima (L_{min}) are determined in each event domain. The following metrics are calculated for each event domain:

$$Y_s(x, y, day) = S'_{L_{max}}(x, y, day) - S'_{L_{min}}(x, y, day) \quad (1)$$

$$Y_t(x, y, day) = S'_{L_{max}}(x, y, day) \quad (2)$$

$$Y_h(x, y, day) = \sigma(S'_{Levt}) \quad (3)$$

where x and y are longitude and latitude, $S'_{L_{max}}$ and $S'_{L_{min}}$ are soil moisture at L_{max} and L_{min} , and S'_{Levt} is soil moisture in the event domain. Y_s , Y_t , and Y_h are the spatial, temporal, and heterogeneity metrics respectively. For a control sample, Y_s , Y_t , and Y_h are calculated identically, but using data on non-event days in the same month. The long term means of the control and event Y values pooled together are removed from Y . Then the mean of Y in $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ boxes is computed.

For every box, the difference between the event and the control samples is calculated: $\delta_e(Y)(x_5, y_5)$, where x_5 and y_5 are the coordinates of the $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ box. A bootstrapping method (1000 samples) is applied to determine the statistical significance of $\delta_e(Y)(x_5, y_5)$. The quantiles of $\delta_e(Y)$ are shown in figures 6.

From Figure 6, we can see that the results are very different between the two models. The ICON model shows generally very strong preferences for afternoon rain to fall over drier soil both spatially (Figure 6a) and temporally (Figure 6c) while also showing a clear preference

for more heterogeneous surfaces (Figure 6e). The strong negative spatial preference is to our knowledge the first time to show up in a global model, which was expected since the model does not have a deep convection parameterization. The globally consistent strong negative temporal preference, however, is surprising, since it is only regionally apparent from observations (e.g. North America, eastern South America, and equatorial Africa Guillod et al., 2015; Moon et al., 2019). The strong spatial and temporal couplings could be related to previously reported too frequent convection in the model Feng et al. (2023). The heterogeneity preference is mostly in agreement with the literature.

The IFS model shows overall fewer grid cells with significant feedbacks and does not show any consistent sign in preference (Figure 6b, 6d, 6f). This difference with the ICON model could be because of the deep convection parameterization which is completely resolved in ICON while IFS has deep convection partially parameterized. One hypothesis is that partial parameterization could cancel out the opposing signs of preferences of afternoon precipitation to fall over relatively moist soils (parameterization on) and relatively dry soils (parameterization off), resulting in no significant preference.

Figure 6: Soil moisture anomaly - afternoon precipitation spatial (top), temporal (middle), and heterogeneity (bottom) feedback quantiles in ICON (left) and IFS (right) models.

4.4.6 Discovering the details: regional analysis of the Alps

While the global analysis in this report helps us understand the overall reliability of the nextGEMS models, the strongest case for storm-resolving simulations is the ability to make detailed analyses on the regional level, everywhere around the world. We selected a few regions for regional analysis where i) high quality observations are available for verification and ii) are expected to show an improved energy and water balance due to improved orography or land-surface description.

Figure 7: Diurnal cycle of precipitation averaged over summer (JJA) and over an area North (left upper graph) and South in the Alps (left lower graph). The colors indicate the different simulations, and the grey area indicates the interannual variability from the observations. The spatial figure shows the summer (JJA) maximum precipitation from the observational CombiPrecip (CPC) dataset from 2016-2022. The analyzed North region is indicated with the blue box and the analyzed South region with the red box.

Over the Alps, precipitation from the storm-resolving simulations is compared with the observational precipitation product, CombiPrecip (CPC) Panziera et al. (2018), based on radar data and gauge measurements. This observational dataset has a spatial resolution of 1 by 1 km and a hourly timestep. Figure 7 shows that there is a clear diurnal cycle of precipitation, both in the north region and south region of the Alps. Most precipitation falls in the late afternoon (18 UTC) according to the observations, where all simulations show the peak earlier around 15 UTC, although within the range of internal variability. The peak in afternoon precipitation is overestimated by ERA5, especially for the southern Alp region. The IFS4.4km simulation shows only a very limited daily cycle in precipitation, indicating that having an adjusted version of the deep convection parameterization on in the 4.4km simulations does not benefit precipitation in the Alps. ICON shows a stronger diurnal cycle compared to the IFS simulations, where the 9km simulations of IFS provide the best diurnal cycle precipitation estimate compared to observa-

Figure 8: Diurnal temperature range (DTR) in ICON (left) and IFS (right) averaged for summer months (JJA) over the extended region of the Alps. Black contour lines indicate the orography. The purple circle represents Payerne, CH station and the brown circle represents Sonnblick, AT (see Figure 9).

tions.

The diurnal temperature range is shown for the extended Alps region in Figure 8 for the ICON and IFS simulations. The diurnal temperature range indicates the temperature variability within a day, defined as the difference between daily maximum and minimum temperature. For summer (JJA), we find the largest diurnal temperature ranges over the mountainous area of the Alps, although this signal is less clear than for winter. Further, ICON shows larger diurnal temperature ranges both over the mountains and the Po valley compared to IFS. When the models are compared to the diurnal temperature range from regional re-analysis dataset CERRA with 5 km horizontal resolution Schimanke et al. (2022) (results not shown), we find that IFS is in better correspondence to those observations. Thereby we have to keep in mind that the CERRA re-analysis is also based on IFS and this might impact the results. The larger temperature range in ICON is in line with the overestimation of net radiation in ICON reported in Figure 2, despite some of it being damped by the absence of a skin layer.

To close the report and to link the regional analysis to the global one, we compare time series of incoming shortwave and longwave radiation for four locations in and outside of the Alps, to verify if conclusions on model performance can be corroborated if data is compared to actual observations in addition to ERA5 as reported in Figure 9. We use four stations of the Baseline Surface Radiation Network BSRN; Driemel et al., 2018, chosen to represent multiple types of landscapes: Cabauw Knap, 2022 (flat grassland; 51.97°N 4.93°E; 2005 – 2022), Lindenberg Wacker and Behrens, 2022 (hilly terrain; 52.21°N 14.12°E; 1995 – 2020), Sonnblick Olefs, 2022 (Mountain peak; 47.05°N 12.98°E; 2013 – 2022), Payerne Vuilleumier and Heimo, 2022 (hilly terrain; 46.81°N 6.94°E; 1993 – 2022). For shortwave irradiance, ERA5 agrees quite well with observations, but the spread among the simulations is over 200 W m^{-2} around noon. Except at Sonnblick, ICON produces more shortwave irradiance than IFS, despite similar or even larger liquid and ice water paths, as already indicated in Figure 3. As a result, IFS generally agrees more with observations than ICON. At Sonnblick, however, where the liquid and ice water paths

Figure 9: Mean diurnal cycles of shortwave irradiance (left), longwave irradiance (middle), and the sum of the liquid and ice water paths (right), averaged over the summer months (JJA), at the locations of four stations (Cabauw, Lindenberg, Sonnblick, and Payerne) of the Baseline Surface Radiation Network BSRN; Driemel et al., 2018. The gray shaded area shows the interannual variability in the observations.

are almost 300 g m^{-2} higher in ICON in the afternoon, IFS produces more shortwave irradiance. At Cabauw and Lindenberg, the model differences are again larger than the sensitivity to resolution. At Sonnblick and Payerne, model differences and sensitivity to resolution are comparable in magnitude, indicating a strong impact of horizontal resolution on the shortwave irradiance near and in the Alps region. However, the coarse-resolution IFS simulation agrees more with the observations at Sonnblick than IFS at 4.4 km. The diurnal cycles of longwave irradiance show a small improvement with horizontal resolution in the IFS simulations. At Cabauw and Payerne, mostly in the afternoon, ICON and IFS at 4.4 km are quite similar and both closer to observations than the 28 km IFS simulation. At Sonnblick, throughout the day, the longwave irradiance in the 4.4 km IFS simulation is significantly closer to observations than the 28 km IFS simulation, presumably because the surface height of the grid box closest to the Sonnblick station increases with increasing horizontal resolution because orography is resolved better: at higher elevations, downwelling longwave irradiance is lower due to the lower temperatures of the atmosphere above.

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

We have the intention to work parts of this report into a scientific publication published in an open access journal. Furthermore, we will present highlights on the nextGEMS website in the form of a blog post, and will present parts of the work on scientific conferences, such as the European Geophysical Union's General Assembly.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

The deliverable was delayed due to the workload and duties of the people involved during the preparations for the fourth nextGEMS hackathon in early March 2024. The delay was communicated with and approved by our project officer.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This work contains preliminary analyses for science deliverables 9.2 and 9.2 in work Package 9. This work has also been done in collaboration with renewable energy company Iberdrola, which is keen on learning about the model performance in reproducing realistic surface solar irradiance as well as wind fields, as well as with the Department of Meteorology and Geophysics, University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022

- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2024
- 4th km-scale hackathon, 4 – 8 March 2024 in Hamburg

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>